
Impact of Alcoholism on Livelihood of Traditional Fisher Folk of Kannur District

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Abstract:

Alcoholism has been there in human society from time immemorial but its consequences have increased considerably in these times. Though it takes its toll from all the poor and vulnerable sections are relatively more affected. A livelihood comprises the capabilities, assets like stores, resources, claims, access etc. The activities required for a means of living; a livelihood is sustainable which can cope with recover from stress and shocks, maintain or enhance its capabilities and assets, and provide sustainable livelihood opportunities for the next generation. Livelihood frame work to various capitals like access human capital like health, education, knowledge, skills etc. The social capital, community relationships; natural capital such as land, forests, rivers, air, wildlife; physical capital, basic infrastructure and producer goods – tools, other productive assets such as appropriate technology and livestock; financial capital such as income, savings, remittances, access to financial services, and political capital; the ability to use power to further political or economic positions. The traditional fisher folk community whose livelihood security is more affected with this. The study conducted among the traditional fisher folk of Kannur district Kerala among people who reside in 11 marine fishing villages shows that there is a relationship between religion and alcoholism and extent of land alcoholism and there is no relationship for alcoholism with other factors such as area, income and employment of someone from the family outside fishing sector. As the incidence of alcoholism in Kerala is higher compared to the other states and that of fishing community being affected in their livelihood security, there is a need of a revisit by the Government on the liberal policy on alcohol followed by the due to its contribution to the Government revenue and provision of employment.

Keywords: Alcoholism, Livelihood Insecurity, Traditional Fisher folk, and community.

1. INTRODUCTION

Alcoholism: Alcoholism also known as ‘Alcohol Use Disorder’ (AUD), Alcohol Dependence Syndrome (ADS) is one of the serious problems faced by a sizable section of population. Medically this exist when a person shows two or more of the following symptoms like taking too much alcohol for a long period of time; inability to control the intake, a strong urge for alcohol, unable to perform well the responsibilities, usage resulting in health problems and social problems. This also leads to mental stress and various psychological problems too. The Global Information System on Alcohol and Health (GISAH) testifies that about 3.3 million people die due to the use of alcohol every year – this is 5.9 percent of all deaths - and is the cause of about 200 types of diseases. Surveys and mortality studies, particularly from the developed world, suggest that there are more drinkers, more drinking occasions and more drinkers with low-risk drinking patterns in higher socioeconomic groups, while abstainers are more common in the poorest social groups. However, people with lower socioeconomic status (SES) appear to be more vulnerable to tangible problems and consequences of alcohol consumption. Given this reality alcoholism will have a negative impact on the livelihood security of the vulnerable sections like that of traditional fisher folk.

2. DATA

In India As per WHO one in 20 men have some alcohol related addiction. As per Drug and Alcohol Rehab in Thailand 14 million of Indians have some dependence on alcohol and needs some treatment. In the case of the economically backward sections this seriously affects their livelihood security. In Kerala the average annual consumption of alcohol per annum is 8.3 liters and this is the highest among the states when the national average is only 5.7 liters. Kerala has the highest per capita consumption of alcohol—more than 1.76 gallons per person a year—in the nation, overtaking traditionally hard-drinking states like Punjab and Haryana. Shockingly, more than 40% of revenues for Kerala’s annual budget come from booze. A state-run monopoly sells alcohol. Kerala State Beverages Corporation (KSBC) runs 337 liquor shops, all open seven days a week. Each shop caters on average to an astonishing 80,000 clients. The paper begins with the explanation of the basic terms of the article like livelihood insecurity and traditional fisher folk and proceeds to explain the methodology of the study. It further goes on with the analysis of the findings and gives certain recommendations.

3. LIVELIHOOD INSECURITY

In the 1970s livelihood security was seen as connected only to food security and this was considered almost synonymous to national and global and country supplies of food. But in the 1980s and 1990s this is seen in a wider frame to include many other things needed for life. Livelihood is related to the availability of all that is needed not just for the survival of people but also for reasonable standard of living where at least the basic needs are met to the level of satisfaction. Views of some of the authors can give a balanced understanding of the concept. Livelihood refers to the basic survival sources that are accessible to an individual or group. It is defined as adequate stocks and flows of food and cash to meet basic needs. It also implies a kind of security, which refers to the secured ownership of, or access to, resources and income earning activities including reserves and assets to offset risks, ease shocks and meet contingencies.

Livelihood security is as adequate and sustainable access to income and resources to meet basic needs, including adequate access to food, potable water, health facilities, educational opportunities, housing, time for community participation and social integration. Each household can have several possible sources of entitlement which constitute its livelihood. These entitlements are based on the household's endowments and its position in the legal, political and social fabric of society the risk of livelihood failure determines the level of vulnerability of a household to income, food, health and nutritional insecurity. Therefore, livelihoods are secure when households have secure ownership of, or access to, resources and income earning activities, including reserves and assets, to offset risks, ease shocks and meet contingencies.

4. HOUSEHOLD LIVELIHOOD SECURITY INDEX

As the definitions testify the concept of livelihood is a multiple concept involving various dimensions and aspects. The availability or access to only certain aspects or dimensions alone does not ensure the livelihood security of people. Assessment on the level of livelihood access and availability gradually brought the need to evolve certain types of household livelihood security indices for purposes of planning and interventions of precision. The household livelihood security index CARE is an eight component measure focused directly on the constraints to family and community wellbeing in middle and lower income developing countries. It helps to identify intra household economic and social dynamics and the coping mechanisms families use to combat poverty and scarcity. The eight components of livelihood security include income and assets, food and nutrition, education, participation, water, sanitation, primary health, and reproductive health. Each of these elements is ranked for availability, accessibility, quality and status on a five-point ordinal scale whose ranges are recalibrated to assess the range of the livelihood security of the people studied.

Livelihood being a multi dimensional concept it is explained by various authors. Gregory S (2008) analyses it in a six fold dimension. These dimensions are: ***Eco Physical dimension*** referring to the extent of access to and control over the natural resources such as land, water etc. as well as the physical facilities like housing, roads, markets and other amenities. ***Economic dimension*** of livelihood mainly refers to four things; viz. Production, employment, savings and credit. Production here refers to the catch of fish basically and in the case of a few it can also refer to any value addition done on it by way of fish processing. Employment may be analyzed from the perspective of optimal employment. The capacity to save, the habit of saving and the extent of savings are important here. As credit facilities is an important need for anyone the source of credit, the extent of credit and the terms and conditions of credit matters much. In general, creation of assets both immovable (building of good houses, purchase of more land etc.) and movable assets (jewels, vehicles etc.) an obvious indicator of economic security. ***Bio Physical dimension*** of livelihood refers to food, nutrition and health, which are the basic survival necessities for a person. This also includes availability of clean drinking water and availability of sanitation facilities. ***Social Dimension*** of livelihood relates to the areas of social interaction and status implications within different social circles at the micro and macro levels. Family, community, neighbourhood and different organizations are crucial here. These provide opportunities to display one's social potentialities in the public domain, which is important for the integrated growth of an individual. ***Cultural Dimension*** of livelihood is associated with education, arts, sports and entertainments. This dimension of life situation manifests a higher level of livelihood status of the people and enhances their ability for creative expression. The cultural dimension of life situations manifest a higher level of the livelihood status of the people and enhance their ability for creative expression. Education is the key here. The emerging knowledge society can offer to anyone with marketable knowledge and skills sustainable livelihood. However, the data available do not give us a rosy picture. Only 1.17% of the marine community could have a graduation and name sake 0.19% has a post graduation (Dept of Fisheries, 2004: 48). It is also not ominous to note that only 9.9% of the age group of 5- 18 have some computer knowledge. This may be read together with the fact that 28.1% of students of the marine community drop out of formal education by the XII standard. (ibid, 2004 52). There is a need to look into all those factors which generate such a situation. ***Political dimension*** of livelihood stands for participation, decision making and leadership. It directly concerns the process of empowerment that encompasses the capacities gained in all other dimensions and implies higher levels of confidence power and authority in oneself and over situations in which they live. As it is evident from the views of the various authors, livelihood security is a multi dimensional concept and so it needs a very comprehensive and holistic analysis.

5. TRADITIONAL FISHER FOLK

The usual meaning is fishermen who use very basic methods with no mechanization for fishing. It was basically use of oars and sails and very small crafts to engage in fishing. But, here it refers to fishermen who use outboard engines and also at times inboard engines in crafts up to 20 meters of length, whose primary livelihood depend on income from fishing and fishing related activities. According to Kocherry T (1984) in the paper “suggestion for improvement of socio- economic status of traditional fisher folk”, the traditional fisher folk are all those men, women and children who earn a livelihood by involving in harvesting, handling, processing and marketing of fish and fish products. Therefore traditional fishermen folk include 1) Artisan fishermen, working on non mechanised and motorised crafts in coastal waters 2) Fishermen working on mechanised boats in coastal waters 3) Workers at fish landing centres involved in unloading, sorting and icing. 4) Workers involved in traditional methods of fish curing and drying. 5) Workers involved in prawn peeling sheds. 6) Workers in fish processing firms. 7) Workers involved in marketing of fish inside the state. They include men, women and children. They need not belong to the fishing castes as well.

Fisher folk form an important segment of the population of the state. Kerala has the eighth position, with regard to the population of fisher folk among the fourteen coastal states. The total populace of fisher folk residing in the state of Kerala is estimated to be 11.114 lakh, which includes 8.55 lakh in the marine sector and 2.55 lakh in the inland sector. Out of this, the number of active fishermen is 2.28 lakh (1.90 lakh in marine sector and 0.42 in the inland sector). The study is done among the traditional fisher folk of Kannur district in Kerala and this has active fishermen to the tune of 5251 as per the Department of Fisheries of the Government of Kerala (2016)

6. METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in Kannur district of Kerala which has 11 marine fishing villages. These are: 1) Kodyeri 2) Dharmadom 3) Muzupilangad 4) Edakkad 5) Kannur 6) Thiruvangad 7) Azhikode South 8) Mattul 9) Valapattanam 10) Madai 11) Ramathali. Out of these 11 fishing villages 6 are chosen in the following manner. There are 4 Blocks in the district of Kannur. A village each is chosen from a Block on random basis. These villages thus chosen are: 1. Dharmadom from Thalasserry Block 2. Edakkad from Edakkad Block 3. Azhikode from Kannur Block 4. Madai from Payannur Block. Additionally, Thiruvangad village from Thalasserry Block and Kannur Village from Kannur Block are selected to give representation to urban area fisher folk. The sample is; The Total Marine Fishing families as per the records of the Government of Kerala Dept of Fisheries (2016) are 5251. The study is done at 95 percent confidence level. As per the calculations only with 5 percent margin of error for 5251 population the valid sample size is 358. This is rounded as 360. Hence, the

sample is 360 for this study. Since 6 villages are already chosen for the study on random basis, all the 6 villages are allocated an equal quota of 60 each as furnished below:

1. Dharmadom from Thalasserry Block	: 60
2. Edakkad from Edakkad Block	: 60
3. Azhikode from Kannur Block	: 60
4. Madai from Payannur Block.	: 60
5. Thiruvangad (Urban Representaion)	: 60
6. Kannur (Urban representation)	: 60
Total	: 360

7. ANALYSIS OF FINDINGS

The results of the study may be analyzed in relation some of the variables like religion, extent of income, extent of land, area and work of at least one from the family outside fishing sector.

Extent of the Use of Alcohol and Religion: The study testifies that among those who use alcohol every day Christians are the majority – 4.7 percent of the total of 8.9 percent. Due to this among the more than one third of the respondents who never use alcohol (35.3%) there are only lesser number of Christians – 10.6 percent of the total of 35.3 percent. The data also show that among the Muslim community 10.3 percent out of the total 13.3 percent do not use alcohol at all. This has serious bearing on the livelihood security of the various communities. It may be further noted that among the 11.1 percent who rarely use alcohol Christians are only 3.1 percent.

Extent of Land and Extent of Use of Alcohol: The study testifies that there is only 6.7percent of the respondents from those with up to 3 cents of land (25.3%) among those who never use alcohol from the total of 35.3 percent of this category. But in the case of those with 7-9 cents of land (7.8%) this is half the size of the respondents – 3.9 percent and among those

with 10-12 cents of land (5%) this is more than half of the respondents-2.8 percent. In the case of those with 16 cents and more of land (2.5%) this is a majority of 1.4 percent.

Extent of Use of Alcohol and Area: more than one third of the respondents (35.3%) do not use alcohol at all and more than half of this (18.4%) are from the rural area. Little more than one tenth of the respondents (11.7%) use alcohol most of the days and the majority of this (6.1%) is from urban area even when the share of people of urban area is only about one third of the respondents – 34.2 percent. Nearly one tenth of the respondents (8.9 percent) use alcohol everyday and more than one third of this is from the urban area.

Employment of Someone outside Fishing Sector and the Use of Extent of Alcohol: The data show that out of the more than one tenth of the respondents (13.8%) who has someone from the family working outside the fishing sector, there are proportionately more respondents from those who never take alcohol and from those who take it most of the days. But comparatively only lesser respondents from people who use it every day and some days are there in the category of those employed outside fishing sector.

Level of Income and the Extent of Use of Alcohol: The data show that from the highest income quintiles of Rs. 15001 and more and from the Rs. 12001-15000 category there are proportionately more people in the category of people who never take alcohol (0.6 percent from the total of 0.8 percent in the highest income group and 0.6 percent from the 1.1 percent from the income group of Rs. 12001-15000) when people who take no alcohol is only about one third of the respondents – 35.3 percent.

8. RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The Government has to revisit its policy on availing alcohol as liberally as we have more than two tenth of the respondents having alcohol daily or most of the days. The move Prohibition had its own lapses when it was tried in various states. When one understands the effects of alcoholism on individuals, families and society at large there is always the need of trying effective ways and means to address the issues connected with alcoholism.

2. It is desirable to reduce the availability of alcohol. This may be done by having stricter norms for giving licence for the opening of new outlets where alcohol is available and also by reducing the number of outlets so that gradually there will be lesser and lesser availability of the same at least a few will stay away from it.
3. A policy of heavy taxing of alcohol though will have a negative effect on the families of the poor in the short run as most of the earnings of the head of the family may go for the buying of the quota of alcohol, it will in course of time reduce the use of this as it is more costly
4. Effective conscientization programmes against use of alcohol have to be thought of by the Government and the various other development agencies. The effective campaign against smoking has brought about a world of change in the country. In the same manner there have to be all out efforts in this line by the government and other stakeholders against the menace of alcohol. This will improve their health, savings and general welfare of the target group.
5. Anti alcohol and drug campaign in schools could be adopted with much profit in schools. We have disturbing news of drugs and even alcohol taking hold of the school and college campuses and this has to be addressed at the same premises.
6. Appointment of professional counselors in schools is one of the long standing demands of the various stakeholders of education. Such counselors can be always a source of help for the students to stay away from alcohol and drugs. If by some reason students fall into these traps counsellors will be able to animate the process of freeing these students from such situations.
7. There is a need for the setting up of more de-addiction centres. Those who are dependent on alcohol have to be assisted professionally with the help of these centres to come out of the menace. They also have to be followed up to reduce to the minimum possible relapse.
8. There is a need to promote more and more the culture of thrift and credit in the grassroots. This will enable the fishermen to go for savings and this will surely improve the economic status of the community.
9. There is a need of creating more and more employment avenues in the country as one of the arguments against the reduction of liquor is the loss of employment of a considerable section of people who are employed in the liquor related venues.
10. The various Non Governmental Organizations have an important role in working with this community which has a tendency to use alcohol compared to others. These agencies can do a world of good by conscientization work and also reaching people who are affected to the de- addiction centres for treatment. There is also a need for following up those who treated through Alcoholic Anonymous and the like so that relapse is kept to nil or minimum level.

9. CONCLUSION

Alcoholism is a problem all over the world as it has undesirable effects on the health of persons, wellbeing of the families and output at work places. However, people from poor socio economic groups are more severely affected with this and most of the traditional fishermen belong to this category. The study done among the traditional fisher folk of Kannur district in Kerala testifies that almost two tenth of the group use alcohol either daily or on most of the days. Given the policy of high taxation by the Government as a deterrent to reduce those who use alcohol, these people spend a sizable part of their income on alcohol and this certainly affects the livelihood security of the target group. The study has also shown that there is a relationship between religion and alcoholism, extent of land and alcoholism and there is no relationship between alcoholism and other variables like area, level of income and work of someone from the family outside fishing sector. As a considerable number of people are affected by alcoholism there is a need to revise the present policy of Government of availing alcohol liberally and take more of curative steps like the promotion of de-addiction programmes and going for better prevention programmes through more effective conscientization package.

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